

SHAGGAR INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

Quarter 1 Project - 2025

Group 45

**TRAFFIC FLOW MODELING IN MESKEL SQUARE
ROAD**

ADDIS ABABA

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Math 1101 – Calculus I

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ABSTRACT

This work intends to analyze the traffic flow in the congested area at Meskel Square in Addis Ababa using vehicle flow rates and travel times collected on a four-day study. The research used 5-minute study sessions on a 60-meter segment at different entry points to measure the average vehicle speed, density, flow, and rate of change to understand the level of traffic congestion.

This project uses observations from the physical environment as well as numerical analysis and the use of the Python programming language to create graphical representations of traffic flow dynamics. Some data used, such as the observation of pedestrians crossing the road, observation of where people park or stop along the road, or observation of people controlling traffic flow manually, is relevant for analysis.

MOTIVATION

In Addis Ababa, traffic congestion at the central business area affects commuters to some degree. Furthermore, the understanding of traffic patterns at the intersection at the Meskel Square is essential. The reason for this consideration is the fact that this intersection is one of the most frequently traveled intersections that the whole city uses.

This study is also learning as it gives the opportunity to use mathematical models and graphs to solve a real-life situation. Additionally, it gives a better insight into human factors with traffic behavior through the inclusion of observational findings and pedestrian activity.

POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS

The findings of this study will help policymakers and traffic engineers design intervention strategies to improve the flow of traffic and alleviate congestion in downtown Addis Ababa. For instance:

Optimum positions and timing adjustments for traffic lights or pedestrian signals.

Implementing traffic management systems based on traffic pattern observations.

Incorporating structural changes such as underpasses, or separate channels for express traffic, on the basis of analysis of vehicle density.

Plans for future development of infrastructure projects as well as for bypasses.

Moreover, this approach can be implemented elsewhere in the city, identifying congested regions where similar traffic analysis can be done. This project will play a crucial role if implemented on a full scale to help design intelligent traffic systems that can dynamically respond to pedestrian and vehicle movement.

PROJECT DESIGN | METHODOLOGY

Approach

1. **Data Collection:** Vehicles flow and travel time data was collected over four days and in 5-minute intervals over 60-meter sections on the east and north entry points to Meskel Square. Peak and off-peak times were considered to ensure well-rounded findings. At the same time, observation write-ups also focused on recording pedestrian flow, unofficial stopping, as well as traffic management actions.
2. **Data Organization:** Data was compiled in Google Sheets, with separate sheets for each day, including vehicle count, travel time, and observation notes.
3. **Calculations:**
 - **Average Speed:** $V_{avg} = \text{distance} / \text{avg time}$
 - **Traffic Density:** $\rho = \text{vehicle count} / \text{road length}$

- **Flow Rate: q** = density \times avg speed
 - **Rate of Change: $\Delta q/\Delta t$** for consecutive intervals
4. **Graphing & Visualization:** Python was used to generate:
- Average speed vs. traffic density vs. flow rate
 - Flow rate vs. time
 - Comparative graphs between days
 - Each graph includes axes labels, legends, and figure captions.
5. **Observational Analysis:** Notes were incorporated to explain anomalies in flow, speed, or density (e.g., pedestrian crossings, traffic police control, minor delays).

Diagram of Approach:

Flowchart of data collection, analysis, and graphing process

Appendices:

- **Appendix A:** Complete raw data for all four days.
- **Appendix B:** Comparison graphs that could not fit in the main results section.

RESULTS

The analysis produced the following insights:

1. **Average Speeds and Traffic Density:** Average speeds were generally lower during peak hours, while density and flow rates were higher. Observations of pedestrian crossings and manual traffic control correlated with short-term dips in speed and temporary congestion.
2. **Flow Rate Patterns:** Flow rates fluctuated with vehicle density and pedestrian interference. Peak hours showed higher rates but also more variability.

3. Graph Placeholders:

Figure 5: Selected Python Code Segment (Example for Flow Rate Calculation):

```
distance = 60 # meters
vehicle_count = 370
avg_time_sec = 31

avg_speed = distance / avg_time_sec
density = vehicle_count / distance
flow_rate = density * avg_speed

print("Average Speed:", avg_speed, "m/s")
print("Traffic Density:", density, "vehicles/m")
print("Flow Rate:", flow_rate, "vehicles/s")
```

Appendix A: Full raw data for all four days (tables).

Appendix B: Comparative graphs.

FUTURE WORK

Given additional time and resources, the study could incorporate origin-destination tracking to understand traffic sources and destinations. For example, long-distance vehicles could be redirected to highways or underpasses, while local traffic could remain on main roads, reducing congestion.

Further improvements could involve real-time data collection using sensors or cameras to dynamically model and predict congestion, offering actionable solutions to city traffic management authorities. This would also allow simulations of alternative traffic management scenarios, such as lane reductions or signal optimization.

CONCLUSION

Traffic flow analysis at Meskel Square shows that vehicle speed, density, and flow rate are highly influenced by peak-hour congestion and pedestrian activity. Manual traffic control and irregular pedestrian crossings are significant factors affecting flow.

By applying quantitative modeling and graphical analysis, this study identifies critical points for potential improvement, providing a foundation for traffic management interventions. The combination of observational notes, measured data, and computational analysis offers a comprehensive overview of urban traffic dynamics in a key intersection of Addis Ababa.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

First and foremost, more than anything else, a lot of praise goes to the name of GOD, who is the beginning and the end of everything. All our successes are the result of his care for who we are today.

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References (APA)

Heald, M. A., & Marion, J. B. (1995). Classical electromagnetic radiation. *American Journal of Physics*, 63(10), 1003–1012. <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.18008>

Road Traffic Congestion Analysis and Traffic Flow Modeling at Meskel Square Signalized Control Intersections:

<https://etd.aau.edu.et/bitstreams/c1e2c117-bdde-452d-934f-f353b39e4057/download>

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A : Complete raw data for all four days

1	Time Interval	#	Vehicle Count	#	Avg Time (s)	#	Avg Speed (m/s)	#	Density (veh/m)	#	Flow Rate (veh/s)	Rate of Change
2	07:00-07:05		370		31		1.94		6.17		1.23	-0.11
3	07:05-07:10		304		35		1.71		5.07		1.01	-0.22
4	07:10-07:15		263		35		1.71		4.38		0.88	-0.13
5	07:15-07:20		381		36		1.67		6.35		1.27	0.39
6	07:20-07:25		342		37		1.62		5.7		1.14	-0.13
7	07:25-07:30		291		25		2.4		4.85		0.97	-0.17
8	07:30-07:35		264		33		1.82		4.4		0.88	-0.09
9	07:35-07:40		212		29		2.07		3.53		0.71	-0.17
10	07:40-07:45		316		35		1.71		5.27		1.05	0.34
11	07:45-07:50		256		27		2.22		4.27		0.85	-0.20
12	07:50-07:55				37		1.62		4.13		0.83	-0.02
13	07:55-08:00		316		26		2.31		5.27		1.05	0.22
14												
15												

Figure 6: Calculated data for day 1

1	Time Interval	Vehicle Count	Avg Time (s)	Avg Speed (m/s)	Density (veh/m)	Flow Rate (veh/s)	Rate of Change
2	07:00–07:05	432	28	2.14	7.2	1.44	—
3	07:05–07:10	389	31	1.94	6.48	1.3	-0.14
4	07:10–07:15	457	35	1.71	7.62	1.52	0.22
5	07:15–07:20	402	26	2.31	6.7	1.34	-0.18
6	07:20–07:25	378	33	1.82	6.3	1.26	-0.08
7	07:25–07:30	398	27	2.22	6.63	1.33	0.07
8	07:30–07:35	413	24	2.5	6.88	1.38	0.05
9	07:35–07:40	433	23	2.61	7.22	1.44	0.06
10	07:40–07:45	406	36	1.67	6.77	1.35	-0.09
11	07:45–07:50	388	34.5	1.74	6.47	1.29	-0.06
12	07:50–07:55	394	29	2.07	6.57	1.31	0.02
13	07:55–08:00	386	28	2.14	6.43	1.29	-0.02
14							

Figure 7: Calculated data for day 2

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Time Interval	Vehicle Count	Avg Time (s)	Avg Speed (m/s)	Density (veh/m)	Flow Rate (veh/s)	Rate of Change	
2	07:00–07:05	432	28	2.14	7.2	1.44	—	
3	07:05–07:10	389	31	1.94	6.48	1.3	-0.14	
4	07:10–07:15	457	35	1.71	7.62	1.52	0.22	
5	07:15–07:20	402	26	2.31	6.7	1.34	-0.18	
6	07:20–07:25	378	33	1.82	6.3	1.26	-0.08	
7	07:25–07:30	398	27	2.22	6.63	1.33	0.07	
8	07:30–07:35	413	24	2.5	6.88	1.38	0.05	
9	07:35–07:40	433	23	2.61	7.22	1.44	0.06	
10	07:40–07:45	406	36	1.67	6.77	1.35	-0.09	
11	07:45–07:50	388	34.5	1.74	6.47	1.29	-0.06	
12	07:50–07:55	394	29	2.07	6.57	1.31	0.02	
13	07:55–08:00	386	28	2.14	6.43	1.29	-0.02	
14								
15								
16								

Figure 8: Calculated data for day 3

	A	B	C	D	E	F	
1	Time Interval	Vehicle Count	Avg Travel Time (s)	Avg Speed (m/s)	Density (veh/m)	Flow Rate (veh/s)	Rate of C
2	10:00–10:05	190	33	1.82	3.17	5.77	—
3	10:05–10:10	208	29	2.07	3.47	7.18	
4	10:10–10:15	187	32	1.88	3.12	5.87	-1.31
5	10:15–10:20	181	28	2.14	3.02	6.47	
6	10:20–10:25	216	30	2	3.6	7.2	
7	10:25–10:30	162	31	1.94	2.7	5.24	-1.96
8	10:30–10:35	214	33	1.82	3.57	6.49	
9	10:35–10:40	186	32	1.88	3.1	5.83	-0.66
10	10:40–10:45	201	27	2.22	3.35	7.44	
11	10:45–10:50	209	29	2.07	3.48	7.2	-0.24
12	10:50–10:55	225	28	2.14	3.75	8.03	
13	10:55–11:00	236	26	2.31	3.93	9.08	
14							

Figure 9 : Calculated data for day 4

- **Appendix B:** Comparison graphs that could not fit in the main results section.

Figure 10: Average speed vs Traffic density(Day 1)

Figure 11: Traffic Flow rate vs Traffic density (Day 1)

Figure 12: Traffic flow rate vs Average speed (Day 1)

Figure 13 : Average speed vs Traffic density(Day 2)

Figure14: Average speed vs Traffic density (day 3)

Figure 15: Average speed vs Traffic density (day 4)

Figure 16: Traffic flow rate vs Average speed(Day 4)